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Formulation and development of a herbal based mouth gargle by using African black honey

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Abstract

Actually for tonsillitis gargles used for this purpose and these gargles are the aqueous solution as we know. For mild throat infections these gargles are used relieve soreness. In this research galangal directly collected from Thailand, poblano pepper collected from Mexico, Chinese cinnamon collected from china, African black honey from South Africa and vasaka leaf powder collected by online used for this research. In this research total works done under the guidance of Guide-Mr. Shibanjan Paul Roy. Mr. Kamal Deka and Mr. Shyam Prakash Rai performed for the practical works and others work and note the reading.

Keywords: Indian mustard, path coefficient analysis

Introduction

In this research organic galangal roots used for the preparation of gargles for the relieve soreness of mild throat infection. As we know about the definition of gargle that it wash one's mouth and throat with a liquid kept in motion by exhaling through it. As in this research the borosilicate glass bottles closed with plastic screw cap used. The other side it will be labelled – For external use only.

Gargle with Galangal

By using organic galangal root simmer 15ml grated in a cup of warm water for 12min, after strain the liquid and add 5ml of African black honey or pinch of poblano pepper. For every 32min use this as a gargle until throat feels up to a relaxant mode.

Method of Preparation

In this research galangal directly collected from Thailand, poblano pepper collected from Mexico, Chinese cinnamon collected from china, African black honey from South Africa and vasaka leaf powder collected by online used for this research.

Table 1: The formulas used to prepare the formulation of Gargle

S. NO	Ingredients	F1-Low conc.	F2-Medium conc.	F3-High Conc.
1	Galangal	9.4gm	17gm	26gm
2	Vasaka powder	2.5gm	2.9gm	3.4gm
3	Chinese Cinnamon	0.1gm	0.1gm	0.1gm
4	Poblano pepper	0.5gm	0.05gm	0.05gm
5	African Black Honey	5ml	10ml	15ml
6	Distilled Water	q.s. to 100ml	q.s. to 100ml	q.s. to 100ml

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Fig 1: Ingredients F1-Low conc. F2-Medium conc. F3-High Conc.

Testing of Antimicrobial Effect

Antibacterial Activity

The bacterial strains collected from Malbazar by Lab. The antibacterial activity of gargle against strain *Streptococcus mutans*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *E. faecalis*. For this research utilization of MHA agar used for the activity to determine the zone of inhibition. After prepared Muller hinton agar and sterilize for 47 minutes at 120 lbs. After into the sterilized plates media agar poured and let stable for solidification. By using the well cutter the wells were cut and swabbed the test organisms. After by using different concentrations directly loaded and plates will be incubated for 25 hours at 37 °C. After the zone of inhibition incubation time were measured.

Result and Discussion

Antimicrobial Activity

The gargle antimicrobial activity contains Galangal, Vasaka powder, Chinese cinnamon, poblano pepper and African black honey. The antimicrobial effect of gargle tested against *Streptococcus mutans*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *E. faecalis*. The gargle showed zone of inhibition against *S. mutans*, *S. aureus* and *E. faecalis* 19.5, 22.75, 24.37 mm at 100 µL concentration. The antibacterial effect of this herbal based gargle formulation has the capability to attach to the bacterial cell and inhibit it properly.

Fig 2: Zone of inhibition (MM)

Conclusion

Galangal, Vasaka powder, Chinese cinnamon, poblano pepper extracts with African black honey has more potent medicinal properties. Our research showed this formulation has potent positive results.

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This research is guided and written skills done by Mr. Shibhanjan Paul Roy who is a Freelancer Scientist cum Author cum Inventor who lives in Race course para, Jalpaiguri. He has 6 international individual research publications with 1 book individual publication with 3 individual patents with 1 groupwise publication and guided in 2 researches with 2 international awards-INSO award and Young Scientist Award and 1 National Award. He guided Mr. Kamal Deka M. Pharm (Pharmaceutics) who is working as an Assistant Professor of Royal School of Pharmacy under The Assam Royal Global University and Former Principal of Crescent Institute of Pharmacy with now Ph.D. Pursuing from 2021, Guwahati with 6 years Experience has 1 patent with 4 National research publications and Mr. Shyam Prakash Rai completed B. Pharm from Assam downtown University 2019 and now working in Bokaro and he is a Sub-Rising Star-Researcher. In this research total works done under the guidance of Guide-Mr. Shibhanjan Paul Roy. Mr. Kamal Deka and Mr. Shyam Prakash Rai performed for the practical works and others work and note the reading.

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